

Vessel Collision Risk Assessment using AIS Data: A Machine Learning Approach

Andreas Tritsarolis
Dept. of Informatics
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
andrewt@unipi.gr

Eva Chondrodima
Dept. of Informatics
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
evachon@unipi.gr

Nikos Pelekis
Dept. of Statistics & Ins. Sci.
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
npelekis@unipi.gr

Yannis Theodoridis
Dept. of Informatics
University of Piraeus
Piraeus, Greece
ytheod@unipi.gr

Abstract—The wide spread of Automatic Identification System (AIS) and tools based on it has motivated several maritime analytics operations. One of the most critical operations for the purpose of maritime safety is the so-called Vessel Collision Risk Assessment (VCRA). Accurate VCRA is a challenging task as maritime traffic is quite volatile, often affected by external factors, such as weather, etc. Addressing this problem by using complex models introduces a trade-off between accuracy quality and responsiveness. On the other hand, Machine Learning (ML) methods can better address this tradeoff. In this paper, we study the VCRA problem from the ML perspective, by proposing an architecture based on the Multi-Layered Perceptron (MLP) model. Our preliminary experimental study over a large-scale AIS dataset shows that the proposed methodology outperforms the kinematic equations-based approach.

Index Terms—Maritime Safety, AIS Data, Collision Risk Assessment, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing number of ship sensor technologies, such as the Automatic identification system (AIS), a self reporting system that allows vessels to broadcast their identification and voyage-related information, is providing a wealth of vessel positioning data well-suited to be used in a wide range of maritime analytics applications [1], [2]. In particular, Machine Learning (ML) based methods, real-time data analytics and big data processing have attracted a renewed research interest, to develop models by using large amounts of spatio-temporal data to solve various-difficult problems.

Effective collision avoidance is the one of the most important aspects of maritime safety [3]. For instance, the expected wide spread of using Unmanned Surface Vessels (USV) in the near future [4] (in order to reduce other transportation channels, such as road and rail) raises high VCRA challenges. As such, in this paper we propose a method for Vessel Collision Risk Assessment (VCRA) and investigate its application using a large-scale AIS dataset.

In summary, the main contributions of this work are as follows:

- we provide the first, to our knowledge, resource of ready-to-use open-source code regarding VCRA;
- we provide an efficient ML-based solution for VCRA, which outperforms related works; and

- we validate our proposal over a large-scale real-world dataset from the maritime domain.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses related work; Section III formulates the problem at hand and presents the proposed ML architecture; Section IV describes the available AIS dataset and presents preliminary results; Section V concludes the paper, also giving hints for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

The current state-of-the-art in VCRA includes formulaic- as well as Deep Learning (DL) -based approaches. The difference between the aforementioned method families is that the former uses kinematic equations combined with ML models (e.g. SVM), while the latter uses DL methods (e.g. Convolutional Neural Networks – CNN) for assessing the collision risk between two vessels, hereafter called “Own” and “Target” vessel.

Focusing on formulaic-based approaches, in [5] the collision risk detection problem was addressed by using quantification techniques (i.e., Extended Kalman Filters). In [6] the authors survey the methods regarding the exploitation of AIS data towards anomaly detection, including approaches on assessing VCR from two families of methods, namely Closest Point of Approach (CPA) Risk Index and Fuzzy Logic. Within the context of CPA-based methods, the most notable work is [7], where the authors propose a unified equation for VCRA, which includes not only the Distance and Time to CPA (DCPA and TCPA, respectively), but also their relative difference in speed and direction, as well as the distance from Own to Target vessel. In more detail, the formulaic approach they propose is capable of calculating not only the VCRA, but also the Situation of the potential collision (e.g. Head on, Overtaking, etc.).

In contrast to the formulaic approach of the aforementioned work, [8] propose a Time Discrete Non-linear Velocity Obstacle (TD-NLVO) method, in which the ship encounter is considered as a process, rather than analyzing traffic data at certain time slices. Their equation takes into account the vessels’ distance, time difference, as well as their corresponding domain, calculated with respect to their length.

To obtain an accurate CPA, Sang et al. [9] propose a position prediction model in order to extract an accurate short-term trajectory using AIS data. Additionally, they propose an improvement over the existing CPA calculation methods by adding the change of speed (COS) and rate of turn (ROT), respectively, and take into account all points in the predicted trajectory, instead of only the latest transmitted ones. Through the analysis of a real collision scenario, they show that the proposed method can help identify and warn anomalous ship behaviours in a realistic time frame.

Iphar et al. [10] propose a general-purpose expert-based method for the risk assessment of anomalous maritime transportation data which, among other situations, calculates the vessels' collision risk using four discrete danger levels. Shi et al. [11] propose a novel track pairs collision detection algorithm for evaluating the risk of ship collision in port traffic using a variant of Douglas-Peucker algorithm, which takes into account the vessels' speed in order to achieve better compression with respect to quality.

Hongdan et al. [12] propose a deterministic collision risk assessment and avoidance model, based on the vessels' kinematic characteristics and CPA alarms. Additionally, Lee et al. [13] propose a collision prevention algorithm aimed towards the safety of small fishing vessels. Further following this line of research, Zhou et al. [14] propose a collision risk assessment and avoidance model for USV, composed of the vessels' navigation safety domain and collision risk index.

Towards combining VCRA with DL methods, Rawson et al. [15] review six popular traditional approaches for assessing maritime risk and compare them to four machine learning methods. Following this line of research, the authors in [16] propose a unified collision risk assessment framework based on AutoEncoders (AE), which does not need to build different models in accordance with the selected vessel domain. Combining VCRA with Computer Vision, Zhang et al. [17] propose a method detecting ship encounter risk within a region using CNNs. This method recognizes ship collision risk by matching images of multi-vessel encounters, and classifies risk level of encounters based on AIS-derived information. From another perspective, Shi et al. [18] model the vessels' trajectories as time-series, and use a double GRU-NN model which was trained using successful encounters of ships in order to "learn" effective ways of making appropriate collision-avoidance decisions.

Most similar to our work, Gang et al. [19] propose a formulaic approach similar to [7] that consists of TCPA, DCPA, and bearing, and create a dataset used to train an SVM model. Li et al. [20] combine an adaptive fuzzy system with ML to construct an Adaptive Fuzzy NN (AFNN). Last but not least, one of the most recent works towards calculating VCRA [21] uses a formulaic approach similar to [7] in order to get the VCR for each vessel encounter, train an ML-based model and, finally, assess its performance.

In comparison with related work, our MLP-VCRA approach differs in the sense that it uses less kinematic equations (it avoids calculating, e.g., relative azimuth θ_T) and uses

$length_O$, $length_T$ as optional parameters (c.f. Table I). Decreasing the processing time, allows us to experiment with deeper ML architectures that yield higher accuracy, while maintaining the overall responsiveness of the framework.

Method	Input	Dataset(s)
SVM-VCRA [19]	$D_R, V_O, V_T, \phi_O, \phi_T, \theta_T$	Non-public
AFNN-VCRA [20]	$D_R, V_R, \phi_R, \theta_T$	Non-public
RVM-VCRA [21]	$D_R, V_O, V_T, \phi_O, \phi_T, \theta_T, length_O, length_T$	AIS Data (Busan Port, Korea)
MLP-VCRA	$D_R, V_O, V_T, \phi_O, \phi_T, length_O, length_T$	AIS Data (Saronic Gulf, Greece)

TABLE I: Comparing our method to related VCRA works.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section, we formulate the VCRA problem and present our proposed methodology.

A. Problem Formulation

The main definitions that formulate the VCRA problem are as follows:

Definition 1. Trajectory: A trajectory j of vessel v is represented by a sequence of GPS records, which is a sequence of timestamped positions, where the k^{th} timestamped position is expressed as a triple of $[t_j^v(k), lon_j^v(k), lat_j^v(k)]$, with the values corresponding to the timestamp, longitude, and latitude, respectively.

Definition 2. Vessel Encountering Process: Two vessels $v_k, v_l, k \neq l$, are in an encountering process during time period $[t_i, t_j], j > i$, when their distance decreases along this time period and increases right after that.

Definition 3. Vessel Collision Risk Assessment: Given an own vessel v_o and a target vessel v_t that are in an encountering process, VCRA aims to calculate the Collision Risk Index (CRI) of v_o with respect to v_t .

In order to assess CRI, some alternative methods can be followed:

- Given as input the vessels' kinematic characteristics, calculate CRI according to a set of equations [12]
- Given as input the vessels' kinematic characteristics, use an ML-based model in order to calculate CRI, as proposed in [21].

B. Ground Truth

Given the vessels' location (x, y) , length, course ϕ , and speed V over ground, the parameters involved in the problem (and illustrated in Figure 1) are calculated according to a set of mathematical formulae [19], [21]. Afterwards, the CRI can be obtained by the dot product of weight vector and membership vector as follows [6]:

Fig. 1: The diagram of vessel collision geometry, adapted from [19].

$$CRI = W \times U = W_{DCPA} * U_{DCPA} + W_{TCPA} * U_{TCPA} + W_D * U_D + W_{\theta_T} * U_{\theta_T} + W_K * U_K \quad (1)$$

where W denotes the weight vector of target factors, and U denotes the membership vector of target factors. Practically, U represents the membership vector of target factors, namely $DCPA$, $TCPA$, D , θ_T , and K . It is a function that normalizes the target factors' values to $[0,1]$. The greater the membership value, the greater the collision risk of encountered vessels. More information regarding the membership functions can be found at [19]–[21].

For the sake of completeness, we include the mathematical formulae for calculating the CPA components ($DCPA$ and $TCPA$) and membership vector U in Appendix A.

C. Proposed ML Architecture

After calculating the CRI of “Own” with respect to “Target” vessel (to be used as ground truth), we create a dataset with five plus two features, namely D , V_O , V_T , ϕ_O , ϕ_T , and (optionally) $length_O$ and $length_T$, and train an ML model in order to assess CRI, without the computational load of the aforementioned equations.

The architecture of the proposed model is illustrated in Figure 2. In particular, we use a Multi-Layered Perceptron (MLP) model, with two hidden layers of 256 and 32 neurons each (chosen empirically), trained using the Adam optimizer, and the default parameters of scikit-learn¹ for 30 epochs.

As already mentioned, out of the seven input features, those related to vessels' length are optional and their usefulness will be validated in the experimental study that follows.

¹sklearn.neural_network.MLPRegressor, https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.neural_network.MLPRegressor.html. Last visited: 26/03/2022

Fig. 2: VCRA Proposed ML Architecture

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

In this section, we evaluate the proposed VCRA model using a real-world AIS dataset from the maritime domain and present our preliminary results and findings.

A. Experimental Setup, Datasets and Preprocessing

The CRI-related mathematical formulae (found in Appendix A) and the VCRA methods to be compared (listed in Table II) were implemented in Python3 (via Anaconda3² virtual environment). The machine we used is a single node with 8 CPU cores and 16 GB of RAM, provided by okeanos-knossos³, an IAAS service for the Greek Research and Academic Community.

For the purpose of our experimental study, we use a publicly available⁴ large-scale AIS dataset, referred to as the “Piraeus” dataset [22]. Out of this dataset, we selected one day (July 3rd, 2018), which consists of 455,145 dynamic AIS records (i.e., timestamped locations) broadcasted by 361 vessels (passenger boats, fisheries, cargo vessels, containers, etc.) within Saronic Gulf, Greece. A map visualization of the 1-day dataset used in our experimental study is illustrated in Figure 3.

As for preprocessing and because GPS/AIS data are prone to noisy and/or erroneous records [23], we drop the records with speed above 50 knots as well as the ones with speed below 1 knot (stationary points). Additionally, we segment the vessels' points to port-by-port trajectories, with an additional segmentation when we detect a pair of points with temporal difference higher than 30 minutes. Finally, we temporally align the vessels' locations using linear interpolation with sampling rate equal to 5 seconds.

The respective source-code as well as the processed dataset used in our experiments are available at: <https://github.com/DataStories-UniPi/VCRA>.

B. Preliminary Experimental Results

After preprocessing the vessels' trajectories, we create our training dataset using the methodology presented in Section

²<https://www.anaconda.com/>

³<https://okeanos-knossos.grnet.gr/home/>

⁴The dataset is publicly available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5562629>

Fig. 3: A snapshot of the Piraeus dataset: AIS positions captured on July 3th, 2018.

III, generating a population of 960,268 samples used to train our ML model, which is split into training and test sets with 80:20 split ratio (1-fold). Table II illustrates the performance of our model compared to [19]–[21], in terms of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) with respect to CRI calculated according to the mathematical equations presented in Section III-B. It can be observed that our approach clearly outperforms its competitors by a high margin (up to 50%) in both metrics, while reaching an overall accuracy of about 87%. Additionally, Table II illustrates the response time, i.e., the latency of calculating a CRI value. It appears that also in terms of timeliness our model outperforms not only the aforementioned works, but also the kinematic equations (ground truth), rendering our model a considerable alternative towards online VCRA frameworks.

Method	MAE	RMSE	Response Time (msec.)
Kinematic Eq.	-	-	329 ± 11.7
SVM-VCRA [19]	0.0572	0.0945	351 ± 1.45
AFNN-VCRA [20]	0.0476	0.0934	314 ± 2.16
RVM-VCRA [21]	0.0359	0.0802	322 ± .744
MLP-VCRA	0.0179	0.0485	311 ± 1.05

TABLE II: Comparison of ML-based VCRA models.

Another experiment, revolves around the trade-off between accuracy and timeliness with respect to the input features. More specifically, we experiment on four variations of our model, depending on which of the “Own” and “Target” vessel lengths we include in the input. Table III illustrates the results in terms of accuracy, MAE, RMSE, and response time. We observe that our model performs the best with respect to all aforementioned criteria, when using both $length_O$ and $length_T$, although the differences from the other three varia-

tions are rather marginal.

	Accuracy (%)	MAE	RMSE	response time (msec.) (min.; med.; max.;
MLP-VCRA ($length_O$)	86.827	0.0179	0.0485	196; 354; 680
MLP-VCRA ($length_T$)	87.134	0.0167	0.0480	201; 360; 684
MLP-VCRA ($length_{O,T}$)	87.514	0.0165	0.0472	192; 332; 638
MLP-VCRA (w/out $length_{O,T}$)	87.207	0.0189	0.0478	197; 369; 695

TABLE III: Assessing the impact of “Own” and “Target” vessel length on the proposed VCRA-MLP model.

C. Exploitation and Discussion

Towards the exploitation of MLP-VCRA on maritime transportation safety, Figure 4 illustrates the collision risk density map for (a) Cargo and (b) Passenger vessels with respect to the surrounding vessels in their vicinity for the test set.

In both cases, we observe that the vessels’ collision risk is moderate ($\approx 20 - 50\%$) within popular vessel routes in Saronic Gulf, as a result of high vessel traffic. In particular, we observe that Cargo vessels (c.f. Figure 4a) have higher collision risk near ports’ vicinity, as well as near the coast, and lower collision risk as they move towards the open sea. This conclusion is consistent when considering both the vessels’ limitations in maneuverability, as well as the general vessel traffic near ports, which creates more “obstacles”.

On the other hand, Passenger vessels present similar behaviour as Cargo vessels near ports and coastal areas, but they differ in their CRI trend when they sail at the open sea. Instead of having an – intuitively – rapid decreasing CRI as they exit Saronic Gulf, they maintain it in moderate ($\approx 40 - 60\%$) to (momentarily) high levels (up to $\approx 80\%$). In contrast to Cargo vessels, which follow different routes, mainly due to scheduling and safety rules, Passenger vessels follow routes which are frequently used by other vessels (e.g., high speed crafts, other passenger vessels, etc.) which may move close to one another, therefore increasing CRI.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we studied the VCRA problem from the ML perspective, and provided an accurate ML-based solution, which combines the versatility and scalability properties of NNs with domain expertise. Our preliminary results on a real-world AIS dataset demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed model compared to the “classical” methodology (i.e., kinematic equations). In the near future, we aim to optimize the timeliness of our framework by further fine-tuning its architecture and its input variables. Moreover, we plan to utilize libraries/utilities aimed towards distributed and federated learning [24]. Last but not least, a natural extension of this work is towards predicting CRI in short-term, thus shifting to Vessel Collision Risk Forecasting (VCRF).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: Collision risk density map focusing on (a) Cargo; and (b) Passenger vessels.

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APPENDIX A
KINEMATIC EQUATIONS

Distance and Time to CPA (DCPA and TCPA, respectively) are calculated as follows:

$$DCPA = D \times \sin(\phi_R - \alpha_T - \pi) \quad (2)$$

$$TCPA = \frac{D \times \cos(\phi_R - \alpha_T - \pi)}{V_R} \quad (3)$$

where D , V_R , ϕ_R , α_T , correspond to the vessels' distance, as well as the relative speed magnitude, movement, and azimuth angle of v_O with respect to v_T , respectively. In particular, given the two vessels' speed and direction, V_R is calculated using the following formula:

$$V_R = \sqrt{V_{xR}^2 + V_{yR}^2} = \sqrt{(V_{xT} - V_{xO})^2 + (V_{yT} - V_{yO})^2} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{x\{T,O\}}$, $V_{y\{T,O\}}$, are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{x\{T,O\}} &= V_{\{T,O\}} \times \sin(\phi_{\{T,O\}}) \\ V_{y\{T,O\}} &= V_{\{T,O\}} \times \cos(\phi_{\{T,O\}}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Additionally, the vessels' relative direction, bearing, and azimuth angle are calculated using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_T &= \phi_T - \phi_O \\ \phi_R &= \arctan\left(\frac{V_{xR}}{V_{yR}}\right) + \alpha \\ \alpha_T &= \arctan\left(\frac{x_T - x_O}{y_T - y_O}\right) + \beta \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the constants α and β are calculated as follows:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 0 & , V_{xR} \geq 0, V_{yR} \geq 0 \\ \pi & , V_{xR} \geq 0, V_{yR} < 0 \\ 2\pi & , V_{xR} < 0, V_{yR} \geq 0 \\ \pi & , V_{xR} < 0, V_{yR} < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\beta = \begin{cases} 0 & , x_T - x_O \geq 0, y_T - y_O \geq 0 \\ \pi & , x_T - x_O \geq 0, y_T - y_O < 0 \\ 2\pi & , x_T - x_O < 0, y_T - y_O \geq 0 \\ \pi & , x_T - x_O < 0, y_T - y_O < 0 \end{cases}$$

In turn, the vessels' speed ratio K is calculated using the following formula:

$$K = \frac{V_T}{V_O} \quad (7)$$

The membership function of DCPA is calculated using the following formula:

$$U_{DCPA} = \begin{cases} 1 & , |DCPA| < d_1 \\ \left(\frac{d_2 - |DCPA|}{d_2 - d_1}\right)^2 & , d_1 \leq |DCPA| \leq d_2 \\ 0 & , |DCPA| > d_2 \end{cases}$$

where $d_2 = 2 \times d_1$ and ,

$$d_1 = \begin{cases} 1 & , 67.5^\circ < \phi_R \leq 112.5^\circ \\ 0.6 & , 112.5^\circ < \phi_R \leq 247.5^\circ \\ 0.9 & , 247.5^\circ < \phi_R \leq 355^\circ \\ 1.1 & , 355^\circ < \phi_R \leq 67.5^\circ \end{cases}$$

Additionally, the membership function of TCPA is calculated using the following formula:

$$U_{TCPA} = \begin{cases} 1 & , 0 \leq |TCPA| < t_1 \\ \left(\frac{t_2 - |TCPA|}{t_2 - t_1}\right)^2 & , t_1 \leq |TCPA| \leq t_2 \\ 0 & , |TCPA| > t_2 \end{cases}$$

where $t_{\{1,2\}}$ is calculated as follows:

$$t_{\{1,2\}} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{d_{\{1,2\}}^2 - DCPA^2}}{V_R} & , DCPA \leq d_{\{1,2\}} \\ 0 & , else \end{cases}$$

The membership function of D is as follows:

$$U_D = \begin{cases} 1 & , 0 < D < D_1 \\ \left(\frac{D_2 - D}{D_2 - D_1}\right)^2 & , D_1 \leq D \leq D_2 \\ 0 & , D > D_2 \end{cases}$$

where

$$D_1 = 12 \times length_O$$

and

$$D_2 = 1.7 \cos(\theta_T - 19^\circ) + \sqrt{4.4 + 2.89 \cos^2(\theta_T - 19^\circ)}$$

(According to the domain experts) D_1 denotes critical safety distance and D_2 denotes the distance at which the final action of collision avoidance can be taken. The membership functions of θ_T and K are calculated as follows:

$$U_{\theta_T} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\cos(\theta_T - 19^\circ) + \sqrt{\frac{440}{289} + \cos^2(\theta_T - 19^\circ)} \right] - \frac{5}{17}$$

$$U_K = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{2}{K * \sqrt{K^2 + 1 + 2K * \sin(\phi_R)}}}$$

Finally, regarding the weights of the membership values, in [21], the authors derived the following set of weights for each term with advice by domain experts:

$$W = [W_{DCPA}, W_{TCPA}, W_D, W_{\theta_T}, W_K] = [0.4457, 0.2258, 0.1408, 0.1321, 0.0556] \quad (8)$$